

Synthesis of quino[3,2-*f*][1,5]benzoxazepines

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An elegant one-pot synthesis of quino[3,2-*f*][1,5]benzoxazepines was achieved from the substituted-2-chloro-3-formylquinolines and 2-aminophenol as substrates.

Synthetic studies on 2,3-heteroannulated quinolines like benzoxazepines and their derivatives have been given importance because of their structural diversity and association with a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. Among quinolines, 2-chloro-3-formylquinolines occupy a prominent position in the intermediate category as they can be utilized for further [*b*]annulation² of many heterocyclic ring systems and for various functional group interconversions³. In one of such investigations with 2-chloro-3-formylquinolines, we have realized the title compounds in a single step procedure.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of equimolar mixture of 2-chloro-3-formylquinoline (1) and 2-aminophenol (2) in anhyd. methanol gave quinobenzoxazepine (5). The reaction is considered to proceed through the formation of an anil intermediate 3. The nucleophilic substitution of the heteroatom [O] at C₂ position of the intermediate 3 leads to the formation of another intermediate 4 which undergoes subsequent dehalogenation and aromatization leading to compound 5.

Experimental

TLC was used to check purity of products. M.ps. were determined on a Mettler-FP5 instrument and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 FT spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on an AMX (400 MHz) spectrometer relative to TMS and mass spectra on a Jeol 300 spectrometer. C, H, N analyses were carried out on Carlo-Erba 106 and Perkin-Elmer 240 analyzers.

Quino[3,2-*f*][1,5]benzoxazepine (5) : A mixture of equal moles of 2-chloro-3-formylquinoline⁴ (1) and 2-aminophenol (2) in anhydrous methanol was refluxed for 4 h. After the usual work up and column chromatography, the mixture furnished bright yellow needles of 5a (80%), m.p. 102°; ν_{\max} 1610, 1574 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 9.09 (C₁₂-H), 8.86 (C₁₃-H), Ar-H at δ 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, C₁-H), 7.89 (1H, d, *J* 8.16 Hz, C₁₀-H), 7.80 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, C₂-H), 7.72 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, C₃-H), 7.56 (1H, t, *J* 7.56 Hz, C₉-H), 7.31 (1H, d, *J* 7.96 Hz, C₄-H), 6.97 (1H, d, *J* 8.08 Hz, C₇-H), 6.87 (1H, t, *J* 7.66 Hz, C₈-H); *m/z* 246 (M⁺) (59.7%), base peak 120 (100%). Other compounds were prepared similarly : 5b (85%), m.p. 195°, ν_{\max} 1600, 1570, δ 2.79 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.96 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, C₈-H), 7.06 (1H, d, *J* 8.16 Hz, C₇-H), 7.27 (1H, t, *J* 5.82 Hz, C₉-H), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 8.00 Hz, C₃-H), 7.51 (1H, t, *J* 7.58 Hz, C₂-H), 7.65 (1H, d, *J* 7.04 Hz, C₁₀-H), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 8.04 Hz, C₁-H), 8.94

- 1,5 a R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H
b R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H
c R₂ = CH₃, R₁ = R₃ = H
d R₃ = OCH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H
e R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H

ν_{\max} 1602, 1575, δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 8.85 (1H, s, C₁₃-H), 9.32 (1H, s, C₁₂-H); **d** (62.5%), 145°, ν_{\max} 1620, 1590, δ 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.0–7.7 (7H, m, ArH), 8.85 (1H, s, C₁₃-H), 9.30 (1H, s, C₁₂-H); **e** (58%), 167°, ν_{\max} 1613, 1595, δ 4.10 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–7.5 (7H, m, ArH), 8.94 (1H, s, C₁₃-H), 9.22 (1H, s, C₁₂-H).

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